

An interdisciplinary approach for Cultural Heritage valorisation through VR: the ‘A cielo aperto’ project of the Riolo Fortress

Development of the “A cielo aperto” VR of the Riolo Fortress through an interdisciplinary approach aimed at the enhancement of cultural heritage.

Federica Collina^{1*}(federica.collina5@unibo.it), Francesca Fabbri^{2*}(francesca.fabbri80@unibo.it), Federica Giacomini^{1*}(federica.giacomini5@unibo.it), Sara Obbiso^{1*}(sara.obbiso2@unibo.it), Gianna Bertacchi³(gianna.bertacchi2@unibo.it), Luca Cipriani³(luca.cipriani@unibo.it), Simone Zambruno¹(simone.zambruno2@unibo.it), Alessandro Iannucci¹(alessandro.iannucci@unibo.it).

¹Department of Cultural Heritage, University of Bologna, Via Degli Ariani, 1, 48121, Ravenna, RA, Italy,

²Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna, Via Zamboni, 32, 40126, Bologna, BO, Italy,

³Department of Architecture, University of Bologna, Viale Del Risorgimento, 2, 40136, Bologna, BO, Italy.

* These authors contributed equally to this work.

Abstract

Immersive technologies like VR have emerged as powerful tools for enhancing the enjoyment of cultural heritage, incrementing their use in cultural contexts. The visualisation of archaeological reconstructions needs historical rigor and scientific transparency; virtual approaches produce highly impactful representations but often compromise scientific accuracy and reliability. Moreover, VR development in museum contexts is frequently outsourced to external organisations, highlighting the lack of expertise among museum staff in managing these tools and the challenges in modifying or evolving their virtual scenarios. These considerations formed the “A cielo aperto” VR project, developed for the Riolo Fortress. The objective was the digital restitution of the Fortress and the connected territorial setups in their original 15th-century form, specifically focusing on developing a VR experience accessible from the East Tower. To create a communicative and engaging experience, an integrated methodology involving interdisciplinary expertise in surveying, virtual environment creation, and historical and archaeological knowledge was created. This approach ensured a historically reliable reconstruction enriched with engaging content to captivate and involve the audience.

CCS CONCEPTS • Computing methodologies → Virtual reality; Mesh models; Point-based models; Texturing.

Additional Keywords and Phrases: Virtual Reality, Cultural Heritage, Riolo Fortress, Enhancement

1 INTRODUCTION

Immersive technologies, particularly Virtual Reality (VR), have emerged as powerful tools for enhancing the accessibility and enjoyment of cultural heritage. Their use in museum contexts has progressively increased, proving to be a valuable resource for audience engagement. The visualisation of historical and archaeological reconstructions has been a topic of debate since its emergence, as it can be highly beneficial for the public but risks presenting a misleading image of the past.

Archaeological computer-based visualisation for research and heritage enhancement was first regulated by the London Charter and later by the Seville Principles [19, 34]; both frameworks emphasise the need for archaeological representation with historical rigor and scientific transparency. On the other hand, these technologies have incorporated workflows and visualisation techniques inspired by 3D authoring in gaming, driven by the growing popularity of video games set in historical contexts. While this approach produces highly impactful representations, it often compromises scientific accuracy and reliability or partial authenticity [48]. Moreover, Virtual Reality in museum contexts is often limited to temporary exhibitions, with its development frequently outsourced to external organisations [50]. That highlights the lack of expertise among museum staff in managing these tools and the challenges in modifying or evolving their virtual scenarios based on the museum's needs.

These considerations formed the “A cielo aperto” Virtual Reality project developed for the Riolo Fortress. The project's objective was the digital restitution of the Fortress and the connected territorial setups in their original 15th-century form without the roofs (the name “A cielo aperto” - Open Sky derived from this), with a specific focus on developing a VR experience accessible from the East Tower (Figure 1). This VR experience aimed to provide a communicative and engaging reconstruction of 15th-century Riolo's Fortress.

This article wants to address these research questions:

- How can immersive Virtual Reality technologies improve the accessibility and use of cultural heritage, with particular reference to the Riolo Fortress?
- Which 3D modelling and virtual scenario design strategies guarantee a balance between historical accuracy and public involvement in cultural heritage valorisation projects?

An integrated methodology involving interdisciplinary expertise in surveying, virtual environment creation, and historical and archaeological knowledge was created. This approach ensured a historically reliable reconstruction enriched with engaging content to captivate and involve the audience. Section 1.1 focuses on related works and the state of the art. Section 2 covers materials and methods, providing an overview of the history of the Riolo Fortress, the processes involved in the acquisition and reconstruction of the village, and the development of the VR experience. Section 3 presents the results, while Section 4 discusses the findings and concludes the study.

Figure 1. East Tower between reality and VR.

1.1 State of the art

Digital technologies for visualising virtual objects or environments are becoming increasingly popular in the cultural heritage field. The Extended Reality (XR) category has been coined to identify the technologies that can introduce the

visitor to a different spatiotemporal context by combining immersive and experimental spaces with real space [18]. Immersive technologies each offer a different level of immersion, with VR standing out as the one providing the highest degree. It involves a simulation of reality where users are fully immersed in an artificial, virtual environment that does not exist but creates a mirage, temporarily persuading the user otherwise [45]. Given its rapid development, the VR system has evolved hand in hand and integrated with wearable technologies designed to enable users to experience immersive Virtual Reality [12]. The most important feature of VR lies in being able to make environments visible that are different from the real ones [3]; for cultural heritage, this is a great asset, especially in the case of places of cultural interest that are difficult to reach or whose integrity is endangered [18].

Indeed, the role of VR is increasingly growing, making it a tool for the study, analysis, and enhancement of the cultural heritage field [11]. VR can also be a viable way for creating remote visiting experiences, for example, in case of sites not easily accessible by visitors due to geographical restrictions, and enhancing disabled peoples' access to cultural heritage environments [23, 29, 31, 37, 43]. In [18] it was employed Virtual Reality to enhance the cultural value of the Castle of Corsano, a regional heritage site that is otherwise inaccessible to the public. The project involved an interdisciplinary team, enabling the identification and development of various scenarios within the virtual environment. The reconstructions were based on a bibliographic and archival sources combination, along with survey data. This approach underscored the necessity of integrating diverse expertise to process and interpret the collected data effectively, ensuring both accuracy and depth in the virtual representation. The use of Virtual Reality is inherently interdisciplinary, serving purposes of both heritage enhancement and academic research.

These visualisation technologies facilitate many applications, including restoration planning, developing reconstructive hypotheses for destroyed or damaged monuments, and conducting digitisation studies to preserve and safeguard existing tangible heritage. By integrating expertise across various fields, VR enables a comprehensive approach to cultural heritage, combining technological innovation with historical and archaeological rigor [24, 56]. In [53] it was highlighted the potential of VR as a research tool for reconstructing archaeologically significant architectures. Their study focuses on fortresses in the western Mediterranean near the Valencian community, demonstrating how VR can visualise research data and architectural elements that have been lost over time. The application enables the superimposition of 3D models to represent historical phases and reconstruction hypotheses, offering users valuable insights into the architectural evolution of these sites. Historical site reconstruction for VR applications demands a multidisciplinary approach. In [21] it was present a structured workflow for creating historically accurate 3D assets designed for immersive and interactive VR experiences. Their work on the Forum of Augustus begins with a thorough source collection phase, followed by asset production, plus the detailed study of historical materials. This process involves an interdisciplinary team – including historians and archaeologists – who ensure accurate interpretation of the sources and available data. This methodology adheres to the principles outlined in the London Charter, emphasizing the importance of reconstruction reliability and data transparency.

The interdisciplinary collaboration essential to VR content creation is also crucial for developing reality-based environments. Photorealism, a key factor in user engagement, has been shown to enhance immersion in VR experiences. Users feel more connected to environments that closely replicate the real world, as these settings evoke comfort and familiarity.

In the enhancement context, the inclusion of interactions and gamification through VR can be a powerful bridge between users and cultural heritage by promoting its deeper understanding and widest dissemination among audiences [54] (Wang, 2024). Virtual technologies provide terrific opportunities for heritage education, also considering how the approach of new generations to cultural content seriously changed [6, 27]. Their application is extremely useful in engaging and

motivating the public with a greater awareness of cultural content; therefore, virtual heritage and its virtual enjoyment are essential for reconstructing the past and digitally safeguarding current heritage [30]. The engagement potential of VR makes it a valuable tool in museum settings, enabling the visualisation of otherwise inaccessible spaces, enriching narrative experiences, and introducing gamified content to enhance visitor interaction. In [9] it was proposed a taxonomy for classifying museum VR applications based on two key criteria: interaction and immersion. Interaction is categorised into non-interactive, mediated, and natural, while immersion ranges from non-immersive to highly immersive experiences, including the use of devices like head-mounted displays. This taxonomy was tested across various museums, highlighting both opportunities and challenges in VR adoption. Despite its advantages, museums face several hurdles in implementing immersive VR technologies. These include physical space requirements, user acceptance of devices, the predominantly single-user design of immersive experiences, the complexity of developing VR content, and concerns about technology overshadowing the museum's primary focus on cultural content. Addressing these issues requires careful planning and integration strategies to maximise the potential of VR in cultural heritage contexts.

In [50] it were identified key benefits, including increased engagement with collections, improved visitor attraction, enhanced accessibility, support for education, immersion, customisation of experiences, and reliable technology. Nonetheless, challenges remain, such as the limited social interaction during the experience. The adoption of VR in museums also introduces challenges related to staffing and spatial requirements. These include the need for specialised personnel and training, significant implementation costs, accessibility barriers, technical and logistical issues, and potential disruptions to the flow of traditional exhibitions. These factors underscore the necessity for strategic planning and resource allocation to effectively integrate VR technologies into museum environments.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials and documents

2.1.1. The Fortress of Riolo Terme

The Fortress of Riolo is a significant example of medieval military architecture, located in the small municipality of Riolo Terme (Ravenna, Italy) (Figure 2). Its history is deeply intertwined with the political and military events of the region, which has witnessed the control of various dominions and noble families. Indeed, from the 12th to 15th century, the fortress gradually underwent some transformations, eventually taking on its present form. The origin of the castrum Rioli is mentioned in a document from 1187, which also references the small church of San Giovanni Battista [15]. From this time onward, the Fortress evolution can be traced through several distinct phases, reflecting the complex stratigraphy of architectural interventions undertaken on its structure [38].

Figure 2. A recent photograph of the Fortress with the East Tower in the foreground.

In 1388, the Bolognese government (step 1), which controlled the Senio Valley, initiated the construction of the first tower and, likely, walls placed to create an inner courtyard [38]. Under the Manfredi family, the village underwent a period of instability, changing hands multiple times before consolidating a stable residential core. During the mid-15th century (step 2), one between Astorio and Taddeo Manfredi, oversaw significant architectural modifications. These included the refurbishment of the tower, now identified as the Mastio, the elevation of the inner courtyard, and the addition of key defensive structures such as the South Tower, the surrounding moat, and the drawbridge granting access to the fortress.

The Mastio thus became a real stronghold, the heart of the fortress' security system and the ultimate defence in case of siege [36]. With the construction of the moat, moreover, the waters of the Canino stream (now known as Doccia stream) were utilized to fill it, giving the village its name, Riolo, derived from the Latin word *rivolus*. However, a subsequent landslide likely altered the river's course, leaving the moat permanently dry [16]. In 1472, Charles II Manfredi undertook other substantial works to strengthen and renew the defence system, including the construction of the West Tower and the ravelin (intermediate step). This innovative circular fortification, housing a *caxella custodiae diurnae* for guard and surveillance purposes, was designed to protect the gateway. Charles II is also credited with other works between 1472 and 1479 (step 3), including the reconstruction of the South Tower and the addition of the East Tower. That was an effective defensive structure: large enough to store cannons, ammunition, and gunpowder, it provided an excellent vantage point over the moats and ravelin and was sufficiently prominent to protect from flanking fire.

Architectural practices between the 14th and 15th centuries often integrated small-calibre weapons into circular towers, used through circular openings hidden in the masonry, while large-calibre cannons were typically placed on the upper level, which offered more space [47]. After passing to Girolamo Riario in 1479, the fortress came under the ownership of his wife, Caterina Sforza, although she never set foot in it. According to the latest studies, the final changes occurred during this period, such as the division of the moat into sections and the construction of the *ravelin of rescue*, which was accessed through the *portella del soccorso* [38]. A reconstruction of the city's late 15th-century layout, based on an ancient map, was depicted by the painter Domenico Dalmonde. In his work, the Ghibelline battlement can be seen on the towers and patrol walkways, although the details are quite small (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Domenico Dalmonte watercolours drawing. Private archive L. Costa, Riolo Terme. A reconstruction of the Riolo Fortress and its village, based on a map from the early 1400s [16].

The Fortress is in perfect condition today, thanks to a restoration and recovery intervention carried out during the winter of 1984-1985 [44]. Between 1996 and 1998, an archaeological excavation was also conducted to restore the moat to its original depth and to analyse the masonry types of the structures uncovered [39].

2.1.2. 15th-century life in Riolo

Everyday life in the 15th-century village of Riolo was very lively. At that time, Romagna was disputed between the Medici, the Sforza-Visconti and the Papacy and then crossed by the fiercest mercenary armies. For this reason, new types of fortifications, able to resist the now-used firearms, were developed in this period [40]. Among the already popular catapults, mangonels and trebuchets, the bombardes make their entry among the siege weapons. The feature of this weapon was that it could also be used as an active defence, since it allowed to counter the enemy siege. A recently restored bombard with the Carlo II Manfredi inscription, dating from 1474, is now preserved inside the East Tower.

In an era of conflict, a significant position was occupied by the blacksmith trade. Many gunsmiths, often owners of furnaces and forges, were engaged in weapons and protective equipment, such as helmets and armour, as well as manufacture and sale: some examples are now preserved inside the East Tower. Much of the profit was also derived from frequent family feuds: people, accustomed to taking justice into their own hands, tended to keep various weapons such as blades, darts, knives, swords, shields and crossbows in their homes [15].

During the 15th century, the sanitary conditions in Riolo was terrible, and the epidemic mortality rates were extremely high. The care of the sick, often entrusted to apothecaries and supposed healers, was done through mixtures of herbs, not infrequently with shreds of snake and magic formulas. Medicinal herbs were commonly cultivated in the gardens of monasteries, the Horti simplicium. Riolo also had its own monastery, located to the east, far from the village, and still known as "Badia di San Pietro in Sala" [15]. The building was built in the 9th century by the Benedictine monks and suppressed by Pope Eugene IV in the 15th century. Today, only the crypt, the well and the characteristic bell tower remain [46].

2.2 Methods

2.2.1. Documentary research

As already mentioned, the “A cielo aperto” project aimed to visualize some of the most significant plausible day life scenarios visible from the East Tower through VR technologies.

Therefore, an attempt was made to find, in addition to the main scenario, other environments that could provide visitors with helpful information for understanding the history of Riolo. Considering the presence along the museum path of materials such as model siege weapons, cannons, weapons and armour, and medicinal herbs, it was decided to create scenarios in which these could be relocated and recontextualized.

A total of four scenarios were identified: Scenario A – East Tower, Scenario 1 – Siege weapons, Scenario 2 – Blacksmith workshop, and Scenario 3 – Monastery herbarium. Finally, rigorous documentary research was conducted to reconstruct these scenarios in as plausible and historically accurate manner as possible.

2.2.2. VR creation

The model processing pipeline saw four main phases:

- 3D acquisition: the data needed for reconstructing the fortress, village, territory, and weapons were collected.
- Model 1: a basic Rhino model of village and surrounding landscape reconstruction with low-resolution textures.
- Model 2: a Blender historicized model where the fortress, village, and territory were provided with historically plausible textures and architectural details and the creation of three secondary scenarios of medieval daily life.
- Model 3: Unreal Engine interactive overall model usable from VR viewer with interactions and vocal guide.

2.2.2.1. 3D acquisition

The acquisition campaign took place on two separate days: the first, in May 2023, was dedicated to the East Tower and the Fortress, while the second, in October 2023, saw the capture of wooden models of the siege weapons.

Fortress acquisition by Terrestrial Laser Scanner

The metric data acquisition was carried out using a Leica C5 time-of-flight Terrestrial Laser Scanner, through which 27 medium-quality scans (1 cm resolution at 10 m) were realized. The point clouds were registered by Leica CycloneTM v6.0 software, using both architectural points and the Rad Coded Targets previously placed on the masonry as homologous points.

The targets were used to reference the various models made by photogrammetry in the same reference system as the point cloud. The total undecimated cloud has approximately 200 million points and was used as the basis for both the referencing of the models and the extraction of geometric data helpful for three-dimensional reconstruction.

The documentation was not limited to the East Tower but included the entire external perimeter of the fortress and the courtyard (Figure 4A). The decision to extend the acquisition to all the external portions of the Fortress was dictated by the need to have available geometric data that could be used for subsequent reconstruction. In fact, although the project focuses on the East Tower, the scenarios designed for the VR application have the tower as a viewpoint towards the village and the surrounding countryside. Despite the impossibility of completely enclosing the outer perimeter of the Fortress with laser scanner acquisitions (the north-west corner in fact has an adjoining building), it was possible to correctly register the clouds, having common points on the west tower, acquired from the inner walkway. To obtain even more accurate data, a topographical survey should have been carried out. However, considering that the main purpose of the acquisition is

reconstruction for VR applications (and not conservative restoration for example), the data collected is sufficiently accurate for subsequent 3D reconstruction.

East Tower acquisition by drone photogrammetry

The survey was conducted manually alongside laser scanning acquisitions. The primary goals of the photogrammetric acquisition were to achieve a detailed reproduction of specific architectural elements of the tower, such as the battlements and the row of hanging arches below them, and to make the masonry texture more visible (Figure 4B). To capture these elements accurately, positioned at a height of approximately 20 meters, a DJI Mavic 2 Pro equipped with a 1" CMOS sensor (20 MP, 2.41 μm pixel pitch), a fixed Hasselblad L1D-20c 35 mm lens ($f/2.8-f/11$), and an image resolution of 5472x3648 pixels was used. Due to the building structure, a circular flight path with specific capture axes was planned. Several control points were placed on the fortress walls, with seven points recorded by the Mavic 2 Pro and the Leica scanner. An initial flight was conducted to evaluate the safe capture of the tower's most challenging side, which connects to the main keep and is closely bordered by other buildings. Further, two circular flights followed, yielding 350 images: 316 taken at close range (~ 2 m) due to obstacles and 34 at a greater distance (~ 9 m) to ensure broader coverage [35]. High temperatures ($\sim 30^\circ\text{C}$) significantly reduced the drone's battery life, requiring an early landing before completing the final mission. The Mavic's DNG files were transferred to the lab's NAS and converted to TIFF format using Photoshop Camera Raw. The datasets were then imported into Metashape Pro (v 1.7.1) as separate groups within the same chunk, with the GPS coordinates stored in the EXIF files removed [17, 28]. Calibration was performed, followed by the manual insertion of visible Ground Control Points (GCPs) from the images. Coordinates obtained by the Terrestrial Laser Scanner point cloud were assigned, and the orientation was optimized. The next steps involved creating the dense cloud using "Ultra High" quality and "Aggressive" filtering modes. The cloud was then cleaned with selection commands and filtered with the "Filter by confidence" command, which removes points with a low number of matches or potential matching errors [1]. The final dense cloud, with 70.487.509 points, was then meshed using a dense cloud reconstruction, and the texture was projected onto the model.

The photogrammetric survey of the East Tower provided a very detailed record of the structure's appearance, with an average Ground Sampling Distance (GSD) of 1.65 mm/pixel. However, this level of detail was partly dictated by the many obstacles in the working area. The decision to acquire the tower from different distances while maintaining a consistent acquisition range for the underground survey significantly impacted the acquisition time. In addition, the environmental conditions during the survey were not ideal. High temperatures drastically reduced the battery life of the equipment, while varying lighting conditions prevented the acquisition of a consistent, shadow-free data set. As a result, additional image processing was required, further increasing the post-processing time.

Figure 4. The East Tower acquisition campaign through laser scanner (A) and drone (B).

Siege weapon models acquisition by structured light scanner

To speed up the process of modelling the elements that would be part of “Scenario 1 - Siege Weapons,” it was decided to proceed with digitizing the wooden models representing the war machines and defence elements preserved inside the East Tower. Specifically, models of a catapult and a cape were acquired. As a first step, the models were taken out of the cases in which they were displayed and placed in the room in a spot where the lighting would not interfere with the structured light scanning operations.

Models were then acquired using structured light projection scanners (SLS) from the company Artec: specifically, given the size and degree of detail achieved by the models, the Space Spider scanner, an instrument suitable for acquiring small to medium-sized objects with a 3D resolution down to 0,1 cm [5], was used. The scans were taken at 6 fps, and the instrument's sensitivity was slightly increased so that the instrument would obviate the problem of slight reflectivity of the models. Each scan obtained was processed using the proprietary software Artec Studio Professional 15 and following the standard procedure of creating a 3D model (editing, alignment, fusion, closing holes, and texturing) [7]. Given the model's destination, a simplification of the polygons was applied to prevent excessive weight from burdening the VR experience. As an ultimate step, textures were applied with a resolution of 2.048×2.048 (the dimensions of the raster file of the texture map). Models were then exported in .OBJ format.

2.2.2.2. Model 1

The aim of the second phase was to create a three-dimensional model that would serve as the basis for subsequent geometric and informational enrichment for the composition of the scenarios. The Model 1 contains the Fortress, the fortified village of Riolo, and the surrounding rural landscape. For the creation of this Model 1 various information was integrated, including digital data collected during the documentation phase, archive data, representations of the village and the territory, and ancient and modern cadastral maps. The model had to contain both the reconstruction of the Fortress, with particular attention to the East Tower, and the reconstruction of the village and the surrounding territory as it must have appeared towards the end of the 14th century. The model is therefore presented as a sum and integration of several models, each with a different degree of definition, which were used as the basis for subsequent additions aimed at the composition of the scenarios (see section 2.2.1).

Data extracted from the point cloud were used for the Fortress model. The reference system has the origin of the axes at the East Tower. A decimated point cloud in .PTX format of the Fortress was inserted in the software McNeel RhinoTM v7. Given the regularity of the architectural parts that make up the structure and the need to obtain a light model composed of a few polygons, the point cloud was used for the specific curves extraction to reconstruct the original appearance of the fortress using surfaces and polysurfaces. Some regular and repetitive elements, such as the merlons, were created as blocks and automatically generated along the curvature of the towers. Compared to the point cloud, which documents the current situation, the roofs were removed to restore the battlements original appearance.

For the village and the surrounding area modelling, archive data and recollected digital data were integrated. In particular, reference was made to the oldest available historical cadastral maps, i.e. the so-called Catasto Gregoriano, completed in 1835¹. In this, the territorial maps are at a scale of 1:2000 while those of the villages are 1:1000². In addition to the historical cadastre, Domenico Dalmonte's reconstruction of Riolo village based on a 15th-century plan was used as a basis (Figure 5). The historical maps were compared and integrated with the current cadastre, available in the topographic

¹ <https://geoportale.regione.emilia-romagna.it/applicazioni-gis/regione-emilia-romagna/cartografia-di-base/cartografia-storica/catasto-storico-terreni-di-ravenna>

² https://servizimoka.regione.emilia-romagna.it/mokaApp/apps/CSTO_RA/index.html

database of the Emilia-Romagna Region³, with the historical descriptive sources of the village and by analogy with other 15th-century villages in the same geopolitical area. Since one of the objects of the project focuses on the military aspect of the Fortress, the ravelin, for which there are no current material traces except for the plan dimensions in historical maps, was reconstructed. Finally, for the Church of St John the Baptist, the bell tower and lateral buttresses were restored.

For the terrain model, regional technical map contour lines were used to create a surface to which a texture extracted from aerial projections in Google EarthTM was applied; these were modified to recreate the 15th-century landscape, mainly according to Dalmonte's reconstruction. In this, it is possible to see mainly cultivated fields, trees along roads, shrubs along watercourses, and some rural buildings. By comparing Dalmonte's view with the 19th-century cadastral map, it was possible to verify the correspondence of roads, water courses, and buildings. The only changes mainly concern the watercourses, some of which were subject to regulation and rectification during the 20th century.

Figure 5. Model 1 obtained in McNeel RhinoTM v7.

2.2.2.3. Model 2

The third phase focused on particularizing the village and its fortress and their historical contextualization; in fact, the main objective was to add more precise and coherent architectural details to Model 1, create secondary scenarios of daily life in the main view, and use historical accurate textures for faithful and optimal graphic rendering.

Model 1 was exported from Rhino in .FBX format and imported into Blender. It then proceeded to detail and “fill” the model with objects, structures, and materials that were historically plausible enough to ensure a high historical accuracy level. Many objects were modelled, while others were downloaded from open libraries such as Sketchfab and CGTrader.

The Main scene consists of the model of the fortress, its village, and the surrounding territory (Figure 6). In addition to elements that characterize the spaces (porticos, wagons, markets, animals, etc.), detailed research and reconstruction work was carried out on the fortress walls, on the village access gate, on the moat that surrounded the fortress and ravelin, and on the drawbridges. As a first step, the fortress walls have been characterized by arrowslit, bartizan, string courses and corbel on the walkways and towers, according with what is still visible. In addition, a texture recalling red plaster was applied to the wall structures of the fortress. That choice, thus going against the collective imagination of what a medieval fortification should look like, was dictated by the study of comparisons [14]. Moreover, the plaster covering of the Fortress' walls would seem perfectly plausible given the presence, already in its 14th-century Bolognese phase, of frescoed plaster decorating its tower (later Mastio). In general, [39] was our primary reference for the reconstruction and relocation of all

³ https://servizimoka.regione.emilia-romagna.it/mokaApp/apps/DBTR_HTML5/index.html

the elements “outside” the fortress, and now no longer or barely visible. The only exception was made for some parts about which little or nothing was known. Specifically, these are the guardhouse placed on the ravelin at the entrance to the village [16] and the ravelin of rescue accessible from the gate of the same name [39]. Given the scarcity of data on these, it was decided not to reconstruct these two elements while waiting to gather more information that could allow a more faithful and historically plausible modelling.

For the original now-lost 15th-century door, we took inspiration from other contemporary structures in the Emilia-Romagna region, such as the Brancaleone Fortress (Ravenna), the Castle of Vigoleno (Piacenza) and the Door of Keys (Faenza). Furthermore, according to archaeological investigations, the moat around the fortress was deeper than it appears today [39], while the data collected with photogrammetry and laser scanners return a modern-day view of it. That led to the reconstruction of the fortress portion covered today and the deeper rebuilt moat. Finally, by the archaeological investigations, the partitions in the moat and the drawbridge that gave access to the fortress from the village were erected [39].

The three scenarios of the siege, the workshop, and the herbarium (section 2.1.2 Scenarios) were initially created as separate environments from the main scenario; inside, elements and objects now on display in the museum tour of the Fortress were inserted and contextualized. In the siege scenario, 3D models of the mantelet and catapult previously acquired, and the hand-modelled 15th-century bombard displayed in the casemates of the East Tower were inserted. For the siege setting, we referred to contemporary historical representations like “The Assault on the Strong City of Afrique” by Master of the Harley Froissart [51], “The Pontaudemer climb” of the *Chronique de Charles VII, roi de France* [10], “Attack on a castle with catapults” of the *Alba Bible* [4], and “The death of Bertrand du Guesclin” and “Siege of the castle of Mortagne-sur-Gironde” of the *Chronique d'Angleterre* [55]. In these 15th-century depictions, wooden siege machines such as catapults, throwing weapons such as bows and crossbows, ladders to scale fortress walls and bombards to break through enemy defences are clearly shown. The blacksmith's workshop displayed weapons and armour parts typical of the period on display inside the Fortress. It was assumed to be located in the main square, at the nerve center of the village and quite close to the fortress. Historical representations such as Gunther Zainer's “Mirror of Life” woodcut from ca. 1475 were used as inspiration for its reconstruction [49]. The weapons represented coincide with those displayed in the museum and of which there is archive evidence. Finally, the idea of recreating an herbarium came from the close connection between Caterina Sforza and the officinal herbs she used for her beauty and other recipes. Therefore, it was decided to revive an *Horti simplicium* like the one that might have existed inside the Abbey of San Pietro in Sala and to place the medicinal herbs now visible in the courtyard of the Fortress. The reconstruction of a small portion of the abbey was based on the few historical sources available [22, 46]. Gaddoni himself, during an inspection in the early decades of the 20th century, describes how the church measured 8 m in width and 17 m in length up to the presbytery staircase. From measurements taken using Google Earth™, the building below the bell tower seemed to match Gaddoni measurements. Furthermore, studying the building from satellite maps, there appeared to be a small porticoed courtyard/ cloister on one side. That ambient was chosen to represent the possible herbarium of the abbey and modelled by recreating the elements visible from satellite images, such as the portico, the perimeter walls and the bell gable. Finally, the herbs were placed in large rectangular terrariums. Once the models were finished, they were exported in four separate .FBX format.

Figure 6. Model 2 obtained in Blender; detail of the East Tower and the fortified village.

2.2.2.4. Model 3

For the implementation of Model 3, Unreal Engine 5.3 was chosen because, unlike other software, it offers a visual programming language called Blueprint, which can be complemented with C++ coding [2, 33, 41]. This choice was motivated by Blueprint's more intuitive, node-based programming approach, as well as the opportunity to expand case studies and testing with this platform [20, 41, 52]. The software also includes a powerful graphics engine, particularly suited to complex scenes requiring efficient handling of large geometric datasets. Notably, Unreal Engine offers Nanite, a rendering technology that enables high-detail object representation through a real-time streaming system that loads data dynamically based on viewing requirements. The engine adjusts rendering quality according to the player's distance from objects, using a Level of Detail (LOD) approach. However, unlike traditional LOD, Nanite automatically generates micropolygons based on screen pixels and object complexity [26, 42].

Another feature, Lumen, provides real-time global lighting, dynamically managing reflections and refractions and instantly simulating shadows and indirect lighting changes. These technologies significantly enhance performance and streamline workflow, though achieving optimal results still requires carefully optimized code and assets based on target hardware specifications [42]. For example, for VR applications on consumer-level devices, Lumen may not be ideal, as it requires a high-end GPU to effectively handle real-time global lighting and dynamic reflections. If the target device lacks ray-tracing support, using Lumen may reduce overall performance [26]. The target devices for the "A cielo aperto" project were Oculus Meta Quest 3 headsets⁷. While they provide good performance for VR experiences, they have technical limitations compared to the requirements of Lumen. Specifically, the Snapdragon XR2 Gen2 chipset with integrated GPU and 8 GB of RAM cannot fully support Unreal Engine's advanced dynamic lighting. According to Unreal Engine's official documentation, efficient use of Lumen requires an NVIDIA RTX-2000 series or AMD RX-6000 series GPU or higher^{8,9}. The VR app's development workflow began by importing the original model created in Rhinoceros into the graphics engine, where a metrically geo-referenced reference level was created. The Datasmith¹⁰ plugin was used, enabling project synchronization between reconstruction and VR interaction development and avoiding data loss. The reconstruction model was then imported from Blender in .FBX format with the textures prepared in the contextualization phase.

After importing the assets, atmospheric elements were added to enhance realism. Following several packaging tests, Lumen was disabled with minimal dynamic elements in favour of static lighting. This adjustment raised the frame rate to around 60 FPS, though performance dipped slightly in areas of high complexity, such as the village. After constructing the main level, three additional exploration scenarios were imported and configured as Sub-Levels within the application. Each

scenario was paired with a Level Streaming Volume, which allowed scene data to load exclusively when triggered by specified conditions in the corresponding Blueprint. To make the map navigable, a series of NavMeshBoundsVolumes were placed and shaped to delimit the areas accessible to users (Figure 7), while to reduce potential motion sickness, the teleport-based locomotion model was retained with only a few additional input actions from the UE5.3 VR Template [13].

Figure 7. NavMeshBoundsVolumes to make the map navigable to users.

Then, a navigable map was created to allow users to explore different scenarios without becoming disoriented (Figure 8). By clicking on hotspots, users can move from one level to another. The map was built with a “WidgetMenu” blueprint class, where coordinates for each scenario were specified. The menu is accessible via an interactive button in each scenario, enabling non-linear exploration of the reconstruction. Each scenario also features a narrated guide, allowing users to explore the Fortress in a “guided” mode or revisit information as needed. Additional components were added to the Pawn blueprint to enable targeting and mapped in the “EventGraph” panel. To make the pointer visible and facilitate map interaction, a specific module was added to the Widget Interaction panel.

Figure 8. The navigable map useful to reach each scenario.

Also, an introductory level was added before the experience, providing navigation instructions through audio guidance and an illustrated panel. This panel can also be accessed on the main level by scrolling down the map. To monitor performance, all level elements were analysed using profiling tools by entering the commands `profilegpu`, `statgpu`, and

statunit. Before baking the lights, the optimized lightmap visualization mode was used to adjust resolutions for static elements, lowering pixel density for larger actors indicated in red as high-resolution. To improve navigation fluidity, all textures were resized to a maximum of 2048x2048 pixels. Finally, the project was cooked and packaged as an APK file for Android devices (ASTC).

As mentioned before, one of the main challenges was to achieve good performance while maintaining the high detail and definition of the models and textures produced. Before reaching the final product, numerous tests were conducted to address problematic aspects such as light baking, surface artefacts and frame rate drops during certain movements. To mitigate performance issues, efforts were made to minimise the number of light sources. Textures and light maps were optimised based on the navigation map, with lower resolutions applied to objects in inaccessible areas. In addition, the use of several materials and particle effects was limited as much as possible. To monitor the impact of different processes on the overall performance, different build packages were created, each corresponding to a specific phase of the project. In the first test, the main scene was imported with its textures and material shading maps, and all materials were created. Then all the scenarios were added, each assigned to a separate level. Next, a project backup was created, the map image imported, initial interactions configured and teleportation within the scenarios tested. At this stage, an APK file was created to evaluate the app's behaviour when executed on the VR headset. In a subsequent project round, button interactions within the different scenarios were implemented and natural elements were added. Finally, atmospheric effects and audio narration were introduced for each scenario. This iterative approach made it easier to identify the causes of any lag or artefacts in the final output. Overall, the management of such a complex navigation map with a reconstructed landscape of approximately 20 km and a line of sight of at least 5 km to Monte Mauro was a significant challenge. In Figure 9, Model 3 can be seen.

Figure 9. Model 3 obtained in Unreal Engine.

2.2.3. *User Experience evaluation*

La nostra valutazione di User Experience ha avuto un duplice obiettivo: da una parte quello di validare il nostro lavoro e valutare il successo di questa applicazione nella sua versione Beta, dall'altra quello di raccogliere impressioni, commenti e suggerimenti così da poter esplorare la possibilità di implementare l'esperienza con nuove interazioni e contenuti. Questo tipo di valutazione, infatti, ha il vantaggio di fornire ai progettisti/sviluppatori un feedback immediato sulla risposta degli utenti all'esperienza (Okanovich).

DIMENSIONE	DOMANDA	RISPOSTA	FONTE	
ENJOYMENT	I enjoy the experience.	5-point Likert scale	Hall (2009); Pei et al. (2023)	
	I found the experience fun.			
IMMERSION	Time seemed to fly during experience.		Schaufeli et al. (2002); Pei et al. (2023)	
	I became immersed in this interaction.		Okanovic et al. (2022)	
	The narration aroused interest in the topic.			
PRESENCE	I was completely captivated by the scenarios.		Schubert, Friedmann, & Regenbrecht (2001); Pei et al. (2023)	
	The environment in general was realistic.		Okanovic et al. (2022)	
	I almost felt like I was there.			
EXPECTATION	My experience was better than what I expected.		5-point Likert scale	Bhattacharjee A (2001); Pei et al. (2023)
	The information level provided was better than what I expected.			
	Overall, most of my expectations were confirmed.			Gao and Boehm-Davis (2023)
	I felt capable when using the experience.			
USABILITY	I found the overall navigation easy.	Pei et al. (2023) (question inverted)		
	I think that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.	System Usability Scale (SUS) (Grier, Bangor, Kortum, & Peres, 2013); Pei et al. (2023)		
	Interacting with the controls was simple.	Okanovic et al. (2022)		
	I felt dizzy while navigating.	Gao and Boehm-Davis (2023) (from question to affirmation)		
	I had the feeling that my real hands matched my virtual hands.			
LEARNABILITY	I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.	System Usability Scale (SUS) (Grier, Bangor, Kortum, & Peres, 2013); Pei et al. (2023)		
	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.			
OPEN QUESTIONS	What did you like about the VR experience?	short text	-	
	What did you not like about it?			
	What would you change/add?			

3 RESULTS

The VR obtained is structured as follows:

- **Introductory level:** this level helps the visitor acclimatise. As a first step, a narrator's voice provides all useful instructions for virtual navigation so that the user can memorise and test the commands in a neutral environment and continue with the actual navigation when he feels ready.
- **Scenario A - East Tower:** The experience begins here. The visitor stands at the centre of the East Tower without its current roof and thus enjoys an unobstructed view of the fortress, the village and the territory. After providing helpful information about the scene, a narrative voice invites the user to look and move around and to continue

exploring the other scenes via the map accessible in each level (this invitation is repeated for all scenarios) (Figure 10A).

- Scenario 1 - Siege Weapons: This scenario is located at the top of the Keep. Several bombards like the one preserved at the fortress and crossbows with their ammunition are positioned around the user. Beyond the battlements along the slope leading to the fortress, an army is on the attack with its war machines. The narrator's voice immediately reassures the user of his safety and provides information on the different types of attack and defence weapons on the scene (Figure 10B).
- Scenario 2 - Blacksmith Workshop: The user finds himself in the village square, in the middle of a market with its stalls. He is urged to enter the first door next to him and thus reach the workshop. Once inside, the visitor can see an array of weapons and equipment typical of the 15th century. In the meantime, the narrative voice tells of the blacksmith's profession in Riolo society and what was produced in his workshop. To continue exploring, the visitor must return to the square (Figure 10C).
- Scenario 3 - Monastery Herbarium: The last scenario projects the visitor inside the hypothetical cloister of the Badia di San Pietro in Sala; looking up, one can see its characteristic bell gable. Around the user are large terrariums containing medicinal herbs typical of Caterina Sforza's recipes. After providing information about the abbey, the herbs and their use, the narrator greets the visitor (Figure 10D).

Figure 10. A. Scenario A; B. Scenario 1; C. Scenario 2; D. Scenario 3.

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

4.1 Discussion and conclusions

Virtual content applied to cultural heritage field is an extremely useful tool for reconstructing the past. Specifically, VR takes on a fundamental role in the effective enjoyment of this content by allowing greater public involvement and motivation and thus serving as an effective means of communication and enhancement of cultural heritage.

The “A cielo aperto” project of the Riolo Fortress was created to obtain a timely and philological reconstruction of the fortress and the surrounding area in their 15th-century appearance, making them usable virtually as an engaging and interactive experience. This Virtual Reality allows users to immerse themselves inside 15th-century Riolo and explore various settings related to the strictly military world of the fortress, the village, and the territory. The narrative voice accompanies the user in the discovery of the controls and, later, in the actual exploration of the environments, guiding him

step by step in the new scenarios discovery and describing in a simple but timely way the objects and places history that surround him. The combination of different skills (traditional and digital) resulted in an extremely useful product from the perspective of historical research, as well as engaging and interactive virtual content helpful for less conventional communication of Riolo's heritage. The consultancy of Professor Enrico Cirelli, a medieval archaeologist, was fundamental for the reconstruction of specific structural elements, as well as for the validation of the overall model.

To address the first research question, the Virtual Reality reconstruction of the Riolo Fortress enhances access to cultural heritage by depicting the castle as it appeared in the past, a state no longer visible today due to its loss and subsequent modifications over time. Moreover, it provides access to various scenarios that would otherwise be unavailable in a traditional museum setting. The development pipeline involved close integration of the virtual representation of the fortress with archival sources, which in some cases required reinterpretations and reconstructive proposals where historical sources were inconsistent. This process not only transformed the virtual fortress into a tool for dissemination within a museum context but also established it as a valuable research product, enabling the practical testing and visualization of available archival data.

The objectives set by the 'A cielo aperto' project were largely achieved, returning the museum to an effective communication and enhancement tool, as well as a historically accurate and technologically advanced product. The Virtual Reality was installed as a beta version inside the East Tower of the Riolo Fortress – Museum of the Faenza Apennine Landscape in May 2024 and to date accompanies visitors on their museum tour (Figure 11).

Figure 11. "A cielo aperto" VR experience usable from the Fortress.

4.2 Future prospects

From this enormous amount of work, it has become clear that, for the execution of VR applications intended for the presentation of cultural heritage, high-performance equipment is required, as well as a more punctual optimisation of the models and their elements. An environment such as the Riolo Fortress presents an extremely complex scenario to manage if the objective is to create an immersive experience while preserving the fidelity of the materials and the richness of the architectural details. For this, technical improvements such as further optimisation of models and textures will be made, as well as the addition of elements such as the rescue ravelin and the guardhouse. In addition, tests will be carried out on different user groups, gathering their impressions and suggestions to improve the future visitor experience. All will make the Riolo Fortress' VR a highly immersive virtual product, useful for the heritage and cultural memory valorisation and for communication to the residents and tourists who choose it as their destination each year.

Finally, to make the workflow replicable, it would be advisable to refine it and foster collaboration between the different parties while ensuring the proper transfer of data from one software to another. For example, it could be useful to formulate a work plan that takes into account the various specificities of the software (such as adequate management of open formats, the possibility of exporting reports, or the generation of useful documentation for the interpretability of the reconstructed data). Similarly, it would be advisable to integrate a method for representing the metadata generated during the project implementation and to adopt a data sharing system structured based on the different processing phases envisaged, as shown for example in [8, 25, 32]. Although the project can be considered closed as far as the deliverables are concerned, the systematization of the collected data would increase the degree of accessibility of the data obtained by laying the foundations for the proper reuse and interpretation of the collected data. Such work would also be appropriate in view of a possible online publication of the models created, but currently usable only in the onsite form provided by the project.

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REFERENCES

Mission 4 Co

- [1] Agisoft LLC. 2021. Agisoft Metashape User Manual, Professional Edition, Version 1.7. Retrieved from https://www.agisoft.com/pdf/metashape-pro_1_7_en.pdf
- [2] D. Aiello, S. Fai, and C. Santagati. 2019. Virtual Museums as a Means for Promotion and Enhancement of Cultural Heritage. *Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spatial Inf. Sci.* XLII-2/W15, (2019), 33–40. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-2-W15-33-2019>
- [3] Doaa M. Alzubaidy and Osamah Abdulmunem Al-Tameemi. 2024. Evaluating the perception of virtual reality in historical sites. In *BIO Web of Conferences. Fifth International Scientific Conference of Alkafeel University (ISCKU 2024)*, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1051/bioconf/20249700082>
- [4] Moses Arragel. 1430. *Alba Bible*.
- [5] Artec 3D. 2023. Artec 3D Space Spider. Retrieved from <https://cdn.artec3d.com/content-hub-files/artec.s.spider-b-a.8-web-it-nop.pdf>

- [6] Carmen Bachiller, Jose M. Monzo, and Beatriz Rey. 2023. Augmented and Virtual Reality to Enhance the Didactical Experience of Technological Heritage Museums. *Applied Sciences* 13, 6 (2023), 3539. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13063539>
- [7] Roberto Balzani, Sebastian Barzaghi, Gabriele Bitelli, Federica Bonifazi, Alice Bordignon, Luca Cipriani, Simona Colitti, Federica Collina, Marilena Daquino, Francesca Fabbri, Bruno Fanini, Filippo Fantini, Daniele Ferdani, Giulia Fiorini, Elena Formia, Anna Forte, Federica Giacomini, Valentina Alena Girelli, Bianca Gualandi, Ivan Heibi, Alessandro Iannucci, Rachele Manganelli Del Fà, Arcangelo Massari, Arianna Moretti, Silvio Peroni, Sofia Pescarin, Giulia Renda, Diego Ronchi, Mattia Sullini, Maria Alessandra Tini, Francesca Tomasi, Laura Travaglini, and Luca Vittuari. 2024. Saving temporary exhibitions in virtual environments: The Digital Renaissance of Ulisse Aldrovandi – Acquisition and digitisation of cultural heritage objects. *Digital Applications in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage* 32, (March 2024), e00309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.daach.2023.e00309>
- [8] Sebastian Barzaghi, Alice Bordignon, Federica Collina, Francesca Fabbri, Bruno Fanini, Daniele Ferdani, Bianca Gualandi, Ivan Heibi, Nicola Mariniello, Arcangelo Massari, Marcello Massidda, Arianna Moretti, Silvio Peroni, Sofia Pescarin, Maria Felicia Rega, Giulia Renda, and Mattia Sullini. 2024. A reproducible workflow for the creation of digital twins in the cultural heritage domain. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14170837>
- [9] Marcello Carrozzino and Massimo Bergamasco. 2010. Beyond virtual museums: Experiencing immersive virtual reality in real museums. *Journal of Cultural Heritage* 11, 4 (2010), 452–458. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2010.04.001>
- [10] Jean Chartier. 1858. *Chronique de Charles VII, roi de France*. P. Jannet, Paris.
- [11] Hwei Teeng Chong, Chen Kim Lim, Minhaz Farid Ahmed, Kian Lam Tan, and Mazlin Bin Mokhtar. 2021. Virtual Reality Usability and Accessibility for Cultural Heritage Practices: Challenges Mapping and Recommendations. *Electronics* 10, 12 (2021), 1430. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics10121430>
- [12] Hwei Teeng Chong, Chen Kim Lim, Ahmad Rafi, Kian Lam Tan, and Mazlin Mokhtar. 2022. Comprehensive systematic review on virtual reality for cultural heritage practices: coherent taxonomy and motivations. *Multimedia Systems* 28, 3 (2022), 711–726. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00530-021-00869-4>
- [13] K. Choromański, J. Łobodecki, K. Puchała, and W. Ostrowski. 2019. Development of Virtual Reality Application for Cultural Heritage Visualization from Multi-Source 3D Data. *Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spatial Inf. Sci.* XLII-2/W9, (2019), 261–267. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-2-W9-261-2019>
- [14] Enrico Cirelli and Debora Ferreri. 2024. I castelli di Ceparano e Rontana. In *Annali di Romagna ed Emilia*. Libro Aperto, Ravenna, 80–92.
- [15] Leonida Costa. 1990. Aspetti sociali ed economici del contado romagnolo nel XV secolo. *Quaderni del Museo del Lavoro Contadino nelle Valli del Lamone-Marzeno-Senio* 2, 5–45.
- [16] Leonida Costa. 1992. Nascita e sviluppo di un castello medioevale. *Torricelliana* 43, (1992), 266–297.
- [17] Matteo Cutugno, Umberto Robustelli, and Giovanni Pugliano. 2022. Structure-from-Motion 3D Reconstruction of the Historical Overpass Ponte della Cerra: A Comparison between MicMac® Open Source Software and Metashape®. *Drones* 6, 9 (2022), 242. <https://doi.org/10.3390/drones6090242>
- [18] Lucio Tommaso De Paolis, Sofia Chiarello, Carola Gatto, Silvia Liaci, and Valerio De Luca. 2022. Virtual reality for the enhancement of cultural tangible and intangible heritage: The case study of the Castle of Corsano. *Digital Applications in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage* 27, (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.daach.2022.e00238>
- [19] Hugh Denard. 2012. A New Introduction to the London Charter. In *Paradata and Transparency in Virtual Heritage*. Ashgate, 57–71.

- [20] A. Dhanda, M. Reina Ortiz, A. Weigert, A. Paladini, A. Min, M. Gyi, S. Su, S. Fai, and M. Santana Quintero. 2019. Recreating Cultural Heritage Environments for VR Using Photogrammetry. *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences XLII-2-W9*, (2019), 305–310. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-2-W9-305-2019>
- [21] Bruno Fanini, Daniele Ferdani, Emanuel Demetrescu, Simone Berto, and Enzo d’Annibale. 2021. ATON: An Open-Source Framework for Creating Immersive, Collaborative and Liquid Web-Apps for Cultural Heritage. *Applied Sciences* 11, 22 (November 2021), 11062. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app112211062>
- [22] Serafino Gaddoni. 1927. *Le Chiese della Diocesi d’Imola*. Comuni: Castel Bolognese, Solarolo, Riolo, Brisighella, Casola Valenio. Cooperativa Tip. Ed. Paolo Galeati, Imola.
- [23] Catia Giaconi, Anna Ascenzi, Noemi Del Bianco, Ilaria D’angelo, and Simone Aparecida Capellini. 2021. Virtual and Augmented Reality for the Cultural Accessibility of People with Autism Spectrum Disorders: A Pilot Study. *The International Journal of the Inclusive Museum* 14, 1 (2021), 95–106. <https://doi.org/10.18848/1835-2014/CGP/v14i01/95-106>
- [24] Aso Hajirasouli, Saeed Banihashemi, Anoma Kumarasuriyar, Saeed Talebi, and Amir Tabadkani. 2021. Virtual reality-based digitisation for endangered heritage sites: Theoretical framework and application. *Journal of Cultural Heritage* 49, (2021), 140–151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2021.02.005>
- [25] Timo Homburg, Anja Cramer, Laura Raddatz, and Hubert Mara. 2021. Metadata schema and ontology for capturing and processing of 3D cultural heritage objects. *Herit Sci* 9, 1 (2021), 91. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40494-021-00561-w>
- [26] Saverio Iacono, Matteo Scaramuzzino, Luca Martini, Chiara Panelli, Daniele Zolezzi, Massimo Perotti, Antonella Traverso, and Gianni Viardo Vercelli. 2024. Virtual Reality in Cultural Heritage: A Setup for Balzi Rossi Museum. *Applied Sciences* 14, 9 (2024), 3562. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app14093562>
- [27] Alex Ibañez-Etxeberria, Cosme J. Gómez-Carrasco, Olaia Fontal, and Silvia García-Ceballos. 2020. Virtual Environments and Augmented Reality Applied to Heritage Education. An Evaluative Study. *Applied Sciences* 10, 7 (2020), 2352. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10072352>
- [28] Kaitlyn Kingsland. 2020. Comparative analysis of digital photogrammetry software for cultural heritage. *Digital Applications in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage* 18, (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.daach.2020.e00157>
- [29] Panagiotis Kosmas, George Galanakis, Vaso Constantinou, Giannis Drossis, Maria Christofi, Iosif Klironomos, Panayiotis Zaphiris, Margherita Antona, and Constantine Stephanidis. 2020. Enhancing accessibility in cultural heritage environments: considerations for social computing. *Univ Access Inf Soc* 19, 2 (2020), 471–482. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-019-00651-4>
- [30] Zois Koukopoulos and Dimitrios Koukopoulos. 2018. Evaluating the Usability and the Personal and Social Acceptance of a Participatory Digital Platform for Cultural Heritage. *Heritage* 2, 1 (2018), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage2010001>
- [31] Christos Kyriltsias, Maria Christofi, Despina Michael-Grigoriou, Domna Banakou, and Andri Ioannou. 2020. A Virtual Tour of a Hardly Accessible Archaeological Site: The Effect of Immersive Virtual Reality on User Experience, Learning and Attitude Change. *Front. Comput. Sci.* 2, (2020). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcomp.2020.00023>
- [32] Vittorio Lauro and Vincenzo Lombardo. 2023. The Cataloging and Conservation of Digital Survey in Archaeology: A Photogrammetry Protocol in the Context of Digital Data Curation. *Heritage* 6, 3 (2023), 3113–3136. <https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage6030166>

- [33] Chunxu Li, Ashraf Fahmy, and Johann Sienz. 2019. An Augmented Reality Based Human-Robot Interaction Interface Using Kalman Filter Sensor Fusion. *Sensors* 19, 20 (2019), 4586. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s19204586>
- [34] Victor Manuel Lopez-Menchero and Alfredo Grande. 2011. The principles of the Seville Charter. In *CIPA symposium proceedings*, 2011. Prague.
- [35] Thomas Luhmann, Maria Chizhova, and Denys Gorkovchuk. 2020. Fusion of UAV and Terrestrial Photogrammetry with Laser Scanning for 3D Reconstruction of Historic Churches in Georgia. *Drones* 4, 3 (2020), 53. <https://doi.org/10.3390/drones4030053>
- [36] Mirella Marini Calvani. 2000. La rocca di Riolo Terme: un monumento ritrovato. In *La rocca ritrovata: il restauro del complesso fortificato di Riolo Terme*. Skira, Milano, 119–120.
- [37] Mario Montagud, Jaume Segura-Garcia, J. Antonio De Rus, and Rafael Fayos Jordán. 2020. Towards an Immersive and Accessible Virtual Reconstruction of Theaters from the Early Modern: Bringing Back Cultural Heritage from the Past. In *IMX '20: ACM International Conference on Interactive Media Experiences*, 2020. ACM International Conference on Interactive Media Experiences, Cornell, Barcelona Spain, 143–147. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3391614.3399390>
- [38] Alberto Monti. 2002. La rocca di Riolo come strumento bellico: le sue forme, il suo funzionamento, la sua evoluzione. In *Riolo e la sua Rocca. Appunti di storia e d'archeologia a cura dell'Associazione Comunità e Ambiente*. Bacchilega editore, Imola, 41–61.
- [39] Alberto Monti. 2002. Lo svuotamento delle fosse castellane della Rocca di Riolo Terme. In *Riolo e la sua Rocca. Appunti di storia e d'archeologia a cura dell'Associazione Comunità e Ambiente*. Bacchilega editore, Imola, 73–84.
- [40] Alberto Monti. 2003. A prova di cannone. *Medioevo* 4, 75 (2003), 90–91.
- [41] Miloš Obradović, Ivana Vasiljević, Isidora Đurić, Jelena Kićanović, Vesna Stojaković, and Ratko Obradović. 2020. Virtual Reality Models Based on Photogrammetric Surveys—A Case Study of the Iconostasis of the Serbian Orthodox Cathedral Church of Saint Nicholas in Sremski Karlovci (Serbia). *Applied Sciences* 10, 8 (2020), 2743. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10082743>
- [42] Luísa Orvalho, Carlos Couto, Duarte Costa, and Gonçalo Leite. 2023. Using Unreal Engine 5 to realistic rendering of scenes. *Kriativ-Tech* 1, 9 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.31112/kriativ-tech-2023-06-93>
- [43] Sofia Pescarin, Ivana Cerato, Enzo D'Annibale, Bruno Fanini, Daniele Ferdani, Rachele Manganelli Del Fà, Alessandra Marasco, Marcello Massidda, Augusto Palombini, and Diego Ronchi. 2023. Hybrid XR Collaborative and Guided Experiences in Cultural Heritage: Brancacci POV Prototype. In *Eurographics Workshop on Graphics and Cultural Heritage*, 2023. 157–161. <https://doi.org/10.2312/GCH.20231171>
- [44] Claudio Piersanti and Rita Rava. 2000. *La rocca ritrovata: il restauro del complesso fortificato di Riolo Terme*. Skira, Milano.
- [45] Anitha S. Pillai and Prabha Susy Mathew. 2019. Impact of Virtual Reality in Healthcare: A Review. In *Virtual and augmented reality in mental health treatment. Medical Information Science Reference/IGI Global*, 17–31. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-7168-1.ch002>
- [46] Paola Porta. 2011. Resti di un'abbazia “ravennate” in Diocesi di Imola: note preliminari. *Studi romagnoli* A.62, (2011), 169–189.
- [47] Francesco Quinterio. 2000. Genesis della rocca di Riolo Terme e analisi del suo organismo nel contenere delle guarnigioni di difesa nella Romagna del Rinascimento. In *La rocca ritrovata: il restauro del complesso fortificato di Riolo Terme*. Skira, Milano, 21–40.

- [48] Andrew J. Salvati and Jonathan M. Bullinger. 2013. Selective authenticity and the playable past. In *Playing with the past: Digital games and the simulation of history*. Bloomsbury Academic, 153–168.
- [49] Rodrigo Sánchez de Arévalo. 1468. *Speculum vitae humanae*.
- [50] Maria Shehade and Theopisti Stylianou-Lambert. 2020. Virtual Reality in Museums: Exploring the Experiences of Museum Professionals. *Applied Sciences* 10, 11 (2020), 4031. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10114031>
- [51] John Frederick Smith and William Howill. 1856. *John Cassell's Illustrated History of England*. Volume II. W. Kent and Co., London.
- [52] Tetiana A. Vakaliuk and Svitlana I. Pochtoviuk. 2021. Analysis of tools for the development of augmented reality technologies. In *4th International Workshop on Augmented Reality in Education (AREdu 2021)*, 2021. CEUR Workshop Proceedings, Kryvyi Rih, Ukraine, 119–130. <https://doi.org/10.31812/123456789/4625>
- [53] Monica Val Fiel and Alba Soler-Estrela. 2021. Interactive Virtual Reality applications for the enhanced knowledge of Spanish Mediterranean Fortress-Castles. *DisegnareCon* 14, 7 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.20365/DISEGNARECON.27.2021.19>
- [54] Hanbing Wang, Ze Gao, Xiaolin Zhang, Junyan Du, Yidan Xu, and Ziqi Wang. 2024. Gamifying cultural heritage: Exploring the potential of immersive virtual exhibitions. *Telematics and Informatics Reports* 15, (2024), 100150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.teler.2024.100150>
- [55] Jean de Wavrin. 1470. *Les Chronique d'Angleterre*. Bruges.
- [56] Georges Younes, Rany Kahil, Mayssa Jallad, Daniel Asmar, Imad Elhadj, George Turkiyyah, and Howayda Al-Harithy. 2017. Virtual and augmented reality for rich interaction with cultural heritage sites: A case study from the Roman Theater at Byblos. *Digital Applications in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage* 5, (2017), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.daach.2017.03.002>